

A ROADMAP FOR ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION REFORM AT THE NORWEGIAN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY (NTNU)

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ABSTRACT

Through the project “Technology Education of the Future” (FTS), NTNU has developed a holistic, systemic framework for re-design of its educational programmes in technology and engineering. FTS delivered its final report in January 2022 – a roadmap focusing on ‘how’, i.e., the concrete steps NTNU should take in the upcoming years in order to implement FTS’ previous recommendations on ‘why’ and ‘what’. This concept paper provides an overview of this roadmap, which outlines 12 *Main Actions* (MAs) within five *quality areas*, plus an overarching ‘umbrella action’ to enable the MAs. For each MA, some *Prioritised Measures* (PMs) are described. Based on a risk analysis we also provide *procedural advice*, emphasising factors deemed critical for a successful FTS implementation.

1 INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

In March 2017, NTNU’s Rector decided that the project “Technology Education of the Future” (FTS) for renewal of the university’s programme portfolio within engineering and technology (in all around 150 study programmes on bachelor, master and PhD level, involving five faculties) should be established, with an ambition to “*promote a new generation of engineering and technology education which is updated in all areas according to international development and society’s needs.*” For a number of reasons, the formal project start-up was delayed until August 2019. In 2019-2020 FTS reviewed international trends and global best

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practices, aggregating a broad platform of knowledge - cf. [1] and the many references therein, which among other things sum up FTS' aggregated findings wrt. international trends and state-of-the-art. This knowledge platform served as a starting point for SWOT analysis of NTNU's current technology education [2] and subsequent quality development in the FTS programme portfolio [3]. By February 2021 – based on the above analyses and findings – the project had also created a holistic conceptual framework for the future FTS study programme portfolio, consisting of a *vision*, *principles* and *competence profiles*. The vision is:

NTNU's technology programmes educate creative world-class graduates – able and willing to contribute to a better world and a sustainable future.

The *FTS principles* were developed as systemic guidelines for further portfolio development to realise the vision, and adopted by NTNU's Rector in June 2021. At 'short heading' level, the FTS principles are summed up in Fig. 1:

Figure 1 The 10 FTS Principles.

The term *holistic competence* in Principle 1 refer to the FTS *competence profiles*, which consist of 12 *competence objectives* that students should have achieved upon graduation. FTS has developed such profiles for bachelor engineering programmes, 5-year integrated master programmes in technology, and PhD programmes. The 12 objectives are divided into five categories, with digital competence and sustainability competence *embedded into* the objectives across categories [2].

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the methodology used when developing both the above framework and the subsequent roadmap for implementation. Section 3 summarises the roadmap for implementation, with Main Actions (MAs) and Prioritised Measures (PMs) supporting the vision, principles and competence profiles. Subsections 3.1 – 3.6 discuss the individual MAs and selected PMs under each MA, while Subsection 3.7 outlines procedural risks and recommendations related to implementation. Section 4 briefly summarises the contribution of FTS and some future challenges and possibilities to follow.

2 METHODOLOGY: KNOWLEDGE FOUNDATION AND THEORY OF CHANGE

The FTS results have been developed in dialogue with key stakeholders [4], the main development done by a core project team of faculty and students, co-led by the FTS project manager and coordinator. The initial phase consisted of an outside-world analysis focusing on future needs, technology trends, and recent and expected developments in the higher education (HE) sector [1]. Through literature studies (cf. reference list in [1]), interviews, workshops, stakeholder meetings, study trips, and participation in international meetings, we identified state-of-the-art and expected trends in engineering and technology education, expectations and feedback from employers and alumni, and governmental expectations. These insights were subsequently “triangulated” with faculty and student input, views from a Nordic university expert group, and official university statistics, strategies and policies. Results were used to propose future-fit graduate *competence profiles* [1] and to perform a *SWOT analysis* [2]. Subsequently, a holistic *framework for future development* was developed [3]: Following a *Theory of Change (ToC)* methodology [5] we formulated the above *project vision* (in ToC terminology, *ultimate outcome*), and eight *long-term outcomes* (LTOs) to support the vision. Furthermore, we identified the 10 *FTS principles* – in ToC terms, *preconditions* – most essential for realising the LTOs [1, 3]. Finally, drawing on experience from FTS pilots, additional surveys by cross-faculty working groups, and integration of FTS perspectives into regular NTNU processes, we assembled a list of *interventions* identified as potentially helpful in realising the FTS principles. Those interventions considered to potentially have most impact – from now on referred to as *prioritised measures (PMs)* – were then clustered under 12 MAs, to create a roadmap for implementation.

3 RESULTS: MAIN ACTIONS AND PRIORITISED MEASURES

Figure 2 Overview of FTS' recommended Main Actions (MAs).

The core of the FTS roadmap for implementation are the 12 MAs, distributed across the five *quality areas* covered by the 10 FTS principles. In addition, we propose an ‘umbrella action’, *Expanded resource-related room for maneuver within the education area*, which spans all quality areas and is deemed necessary to enable implementation of the 12 MAs. At ‘heading’ level, the MAs, their distribution between quality areas, and the ‘umbrella’ action are illustrated in Fig. 2.

3.1 Main Actions for future graduate competence profiles

MA1: *Redesign the programme portfolio’s common elements and signature courses.* This MA supports FTS principles I and II. Elements and courses shared between many programmes in the FTS portfolio include: *Introduction to the Engineering Profession, Introductory Course in Philosophy, Technology Management, Experts-in-a-Team*, and common courses in mathematics, statistics and IT. *PMs* include:

- Review and revise the content and pedagogical approaches in all common elements and signature courses (using FTS principles III – V as guidelines)
- Establish dedicated introductory courses and sequential ‘ladders’ of core courses in all engineering and technology programmes
- Integrate team-based and project-based learning on authentic and ‘wicked’ problems in courses from the early phases of the programmes.

MA2: *Redesign each individual study programme.* This MA supports FTS principles I and II. MA2 does the same for the *programme-specific* elements as MA1 does for the common elements. Together they lead to a complete redesign of each programme - an operation at the very core of the FTS implementation. *PMs* include:

- During its next periodic review, gap-analyse each study programme against FTS principles I - VI and the FTS competence profiles
- From the general FTS competence profiles, derive a programme-specific competence profile and a Learning Outcome Description
- Using e.g. a programme-to-course mapping matrix, redesign each programme’s course plan, learning activities and assessment methods to align with the new profile and FTS principles, and create an *integrated programme description* [6].

3.2 Main Actions for pedagogical learning environment

MA 3: *Strengthen Student-Teacher Interaction.* This MA supports FTS principles III and IV. It is known to be important for students’ motivation, retention and learning that the *first years of their studies* promote learning, belonging, well-being and identity. Hence *PMs* include:

- Prioritise more teaching capacity to the first part of the study programmes
- Strengthen collaboration between programme core and discipline departments, to facilitate more contextual learning in e.g. mathematics and statistics courses
- Strengthen along-the-way assessment, student feedback and dialogue
- Focus on teaching as a *collective responsibility*, and *collaborative teacher teams*.

MA4: *Expect educational competence development and engagement in quality development.* This MA supports FTS principle V. NTNU’s current guidelines and

personnel regulations clearly emphasise the importance of documented educational competence for appointments or promotion, but should be more clear wrt. *expectations on the actual use of such competence in development of educational quality after appointment*. The *PMs* are therefore:

- Revise guidelines for academic appointment and onboarding to emphasise educational development
- Discuss educational competence and quality work in annual appraisal interviews.

MA5: Facilitate and support educational competence development. This MA supports FTS principle V. Here, the following points have been identified as particularly important: That a relevant *offer of courses* and a good *support apparatus* are available, that teachers are given *time* to develop educationally, that *heads of departments* and *study programme managers* also develop educational competence, and that the institution recognises *the value* of educational competence development and quality work. The *PMs* therefore include:

- Further strengthening institutional support and course offerings for educational competence development – and freeing up teachers' time to use it
- Strengthening NTNU's *Centre for Science and Engineering Education Development* (SEED), and establishing didactic resources at individual faculties
- Creating FTS-specific development modules for study programme managers, and including basic educational competence modules in NTNU's development programme for Heads of Department
- Revision of NTNU's incentive structures related to educational development.

3.3 Main Actions for programme and portfolio development

MA6: Strengthen educational leadership at programme and portfolio level. This MA supports FTS principles VI and VII. *PMs* include:

- Revise mandates and clarify process descriptions in the education quality system
- Strengthen dialogue between study programme leaders, faculties and departments on programme development, and provide study programme leaders with dedicated programme development funds
- Create arenas promoting educational dialogue and culture building, and dissemination of educational practice, across study programmes and faculties.

MA7: Update NTNU's support systems for learning, and for educational quality work. This MA supports FTS principles VI and VII, and shall ensure that NTNU's educational support systems are appropriate, functional and suitable for services and quality processes which are important for FTS implementation. *PMs* include:

- Adapt administrative IT systems and learning support systems to actively facilitate programme and portfolio development in accordance with FTS principles
- Facilitate automated data capture to enable knowledge-based educational quality development. In particular, strengthen *the programme perspective*.
- Enhance NTNU's ability to analyse societal needs and technology trends, to strengthen the knowledge base for portfolio development and dimensioning.

MA8: *Enable more holistic programme portfolio development.* This MA supports FTS principle VI. *PMs* include:

- Assess and if necessary revise the structural constraints for NTNU's programme types, to ensure they are aligned with FTS principles and competence profiles
- Regularly revise the overall FTS portfolio's orientation, balance and scope with particular focus on academic-strategic *relevance*, academic and economic *sustainability*, good *communicability* and appropriate *agility*.

Note that MA6 and MA7 support MA8 - educational leadership and well-functioning support systems are both vital to programme portfolio development.

3.4 Main Actions for collaboration and interaction

MA9: *Expand NTNU's toolbox for collaboration with working life.* This MA supports FTS principle IX. *PMs* include:

- Introduce elective courses giving ECTS credits for *supervised professional practice* in all technology and engineering programmes.
- Strengthen strategic working life collaborations on *projects and student assignments*, at all levels from individual courses to master's and PhD theses.
- Expand *industry sabbaticals* as a collaboration instrument.
- Link *Business Networks* to all study programmes, focusing on programme recruitment, retention and relevance.
- Develop a scheme for *practice-oriented international student exchange*.

MA10: *Clarify the institutional strategy on lifelong learning and develop instruments for its implementation.* This MA supports FTS principle IX. Lifelong learning (LLL) has been high on the political agenda for several years, and the FTS mandate particularly emphasises this issue. *PMs* include:

- Develop a clear institutional strategy and associated new tools for LLL
- Facilitate open online access of learning resources in all ordinary courses
- Incentivise development of *small, digitally delivered course modules* – facilitating future micro-credentials, cross-disciplinary course design and integrated learning.

MA11: *Strengthen international collaboration on development of technology education.* This MA supports FTS principle VIII, and serve to heighten NTNU's international visibility, and enable sharing with and learning from international education networks. *PMs* include:

- Stimulate NTNU's teachers to participate in international education networks
- Prioritise participation in international education initiatives and consortia where NTNU can be inspired by internationally leading technical universities
- Link international student exchange agreements systematically to institutional collaboration on educational research and development

3.5 Main Action for physical, digital and psychosocial learning environment

MA12: *Develop campus solutions for learning, health and well-being.* This MA supports FTS principle X. NTNU's ongoing *Unified Campus* (UC) project [7] aims to

gather NTNU's academic communities in Trondheim from scattered locations to one unified campus. The UC project's *Thematic User Groups (TUGs)* on *Learning Spaces* and *Campus Hubs* have recently developed principles for learning space and campus hub development which we view to be in line with FTS' principles. The *PMs* are thus:

- Develop new learning spaces and campus hubs according to the principles developed by the corresponding TUGs in NTNU's UC project.
- Establish a physical 'Learning Hub' centrally located at NTNU's campus, as a user-centered '*one stop shop*' support centre for teachers in their development of educational competence and new forms of teaching.

3.6 Enabling Main Actions by increasing resource-related room to maneuver

It is not realistic to carry out the MAs and associated PMs without expanding – at least temporarily - the *resource-related room for maneuver* within NTNU's education area. There are significant cost drivers related to, e.g., capacity building, competence development, infrastructure development, and pedagogical renewal. FTS therefore proposes the enabling 'umbrella action' *Expanding the resource-related room for maneuver within education*, with the following PMs:

- Establish '*NTNU Education Boost 2030*' – a temporary institutional initiative to increase strategic investment in education, to restructure the educational portfolio and improve its quality, and thus reduce drop-out rates, strengthen throughput and improve recruitment - and over time increase education-related income
- Critically review resource use on teaching and assessment in the FTS portfolio - to uncover activities and practices that should be deprioritised, changed, or terminated – so that resources can be reallocated to support FTS implementation
- Strategically re-dimension the FTS portfolio (programmes and courses) to ensure that long-term portfolio development can be carried out on the desired quality level within the resource frame expected to be available after 2030
- Actively seek to expand funding within the field of education by means of external sources, e.g., project funds from the Norwegian Directorate for Higher Education and Skills or Erasmus+, and industry co-funding e.g. for professorships, education infrastructure, continuing education, and internships.

3.7 Responsibilities, risks, and procedural advice

FTS' final report [2] includes a tabular overview of all MAs and PMs, with proposed timelines, qualitative assessment of resource needs, and assigned main implementation responsables. To maximise clarity, it also contains six sub-tables focusing on one main responsible each: The Rector, NTNU's executive committees for engineering education, faculties, departments, programme leaders, and course coordinators. Table 1 shows the PMs where the *departments* are main responsables.

Table 1. Prioritised measures for which the departments are to be primarily responsible.

Quality Area	MA	PMs for which the departments are primarily responsible
Pedagogical learning environment	3: Strengthen student - teacher interaction	3.a: Prioritise more teaching capacity to lower-year courses 3.d: Facilitate collective teaching responsibility (for the dept's courses)
	4: Expect educational competence development and dedicated quality work	4.b: Discuss educational competence and quality assurance work in performance assessment interviews
	5: Facilitate educational competence development	5.a: Develop support and courses for teachers' educational competence development – and free up time for them to use the courses (department's responsibility is to free up time for its own teachers)
		5.b: Develop subject-specific didactic resources at departmental level
Collaboration and interaction	11: Strengthen international collaboration on technology education development	11.a: Stimulate teachers to participate in international education networks

In Oct. 2021, Dr. *Ruth Graham* did a snapshot FTS review [8], identifying implementation-related risks. Graham found that *“the single biggest risk facing the successful delivery of the FTS vision appears to be ... the governance and ownership of the change effort post-January 2022.”* In response, FTS has given NTNU the following *procedural advice* regarding the change process:

1. *The Rector, executive committees, deans, department heads, study programme leaders and course coordinators must first take ownership of the FTS proposals.*
2. *Subsequently, carry out a broad, thorough anchoring and motivation process.*
3. *Then make and communicate clear decisions on MAs and PMs to be prioritised.*
4. *All parties assigned as primarily responsible for adopted decisions must then be given a clear mandate and resources to follow up their responsibility.*
5. *The follow-up should be integrated in NTNU's regular, periodic quality processes.*
6. *Re-schedule resources to support prioritised follow-up at all organisation levels.*
7. *Link reasonable indicators to the follow-up - and ensure that they are monitored.*
8. *Along the line, gain experience by running pilot projects within selected areas.*
9. *For the first two years, implement a central support function for coordination, communication and various operational work related to the FTS follow-up.*

4 SUMMARY

The FTS roadmap has been designed to give NTNU's technology and engineering education a significant and systemic boost. The most important job – the implementation - is now underway; the final report is subject to organisational review in the spring of 2022, with actual implementation expected to start in the fall. This will require wise, visionary and inclusive leadership, prioritisation of fresh resources to education, and commitment, motivation and effort from the entire organisation. Several FTS proposals challenge established NTNU traditions, frameworks, cultures and practices. However, if successful, the change process should provide great opportunities and could potentially increase NTNU's international visibility.

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